

A Case Control Study to Investigate Cord Blood Mean Platelet Volume (MPV) of Infants of Diabetic Mothers (IDM)

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Received: 26-5-2023 Revised: 10-06-2023 / Accepted: 29-06-2023

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to investigate cord blood mean platelet volume (MPV) of infants of diabetic mothers (IDM).

Methods: Present study was conducted at Department of Physiology in Nalanda Medical College, Patna, Bihar, India. It was a prospective case control study conducted in 100 newborns. The approval of ethics committee was obtained. They were divided in to 50 Diabetic women with singleton pregnancy between 37-40 gestational weeks (study group) and 50 age matched healthy pregnant women as control group.

Results: The result showed significant difference in maternal, BMI and HbA1c between the study groups. Apgar score assessment at birth did not show any significant difference between two groups. Demographic characteristics of the newborns between two groups were not significant. Platelet count was significantly higher in control group than in diabetic group. MPV was significantly higher in IDM group. There was no significant difference in Platelet distribution width (PDW) between two groups.

Conclusion: Mean Platelet volume and other platelet-related parameters is a simple procedure, available in most hospital laboratories. It is useful for representing the potential oxidative stress of IDM. Hence, there is need to create more awareness by pre-pregnancy counselling of know diabetics as well as screening for potential gestational diabetics. MPV may be used as a marker for follow-up of diabetic patients.

Keywords: Cord blood, Gestational diabetes mellitus, Mean platelet volume, Morbidity, Oxidative stress

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Introduction

Maternal hyperglycemia leads to elevated blood glucose levels in the fetus and a metabolically abnormal fetal milieu. This may result in birth defects, spontaneous abortions, macrosomia, asphyxia, respiratory distress syndrome and other metabolic complications. [1-3] Infants of diabetic mothers may be at an increased

risk for developing diabetes and/or obesity later in life. [1] Controlling hyperglycemia during pregnancy reduces these complications in their offspring. In addition to hyperglycemia, hyperketonemia also occurs in type 1 and some type 2 diabetic patients. [4] Hyperketonemia can cause increased

circulating levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines. [5-7]

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) refers to the state of hyperglycemia during the second half of pregnancy, with no pre-existing diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, affecting about 14% of pregnancies worldwide. [8] An uncomplicated pregnancy is characterized by insulin resistance, which increases with advancing gestation in order to secure a high glucose supply to the fetus; this may be attributed to hormones and cytokines, including TNF α , IL-6 and adipokines (resistin and leptin) produced by the placenta. [9,10] TNF α is considered as the most important factor that can predict insulin resistance in pregnancy, by impeding insulin actions via impaired intracellular signaling. [11] The adipokines leptin and resistin have also emerged as potential causes of insulin resistance, as they interfere with insulin receptor substrate-1 and lead to its degradation. [12] In GDM, the decreased insulin sensitivity that occurs during pregnancy is exaggerated, due to an alteration of the inflammatory profile; there is excessive production of pro-inflammatory molecules by the placenta, which leads to a hyperglycemic phenotype. [13]

Newborns from diabetic mothers are more frequently born prematurely, large for the gestational age and with risk of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and subsequently, exposed to a higher risk of perinatal distress, hypoxia, metabolic stress and hematologic alterations. Probably, classically described modifications such as myocardial hypertrophy, accelerated growth, polycythemia, modified blood rheology and cerebral perfusion found in the intra-uterine life are due to the chronic adaptation mechanisms to the continuous metabolic stress of hyperglycemia. [14,15] Hypoglycemia, hypocalcemia, hyperbilirubinemia and polycythemia are some of the complications seen in the

IDM. Besides increase in perinatal mortality, there is increased risk of developing obesity, impaired glucose tolerance and DM in childhood period. [16] Patients with DM show altered platelet function, including decreased nitric oxide synthase activity and increased peroxynitrite production. [17-19] Platelet volumes are direct indicators of increased platelet synthesis. [20]

The aim of the present study was to investigate cord blood mean platelet volume (MPV) of infants of diabetic mothers (IDM).

Materials and Methods

Present study was conducted at Department of Physiology in Nalanda Medical College, Patna, Bihar, India. It was a prospective case control study conducted in 100 newborns. The approval of ethics committee was obtained. They were divided into 50 Diabetic women with singleton pregnancy between 37-40 gestational weeks (study group) and 50 age matched healthy pregnant women as control group.

Patients who refused to participate, those suffering from cardiovascular disease, thyroid disorder, anaemia, toxemia of pregnancy and multiple gestation were excluded. All subjects were informed in detail about aim, objectives and procedure of the study and written consent was taken for conduct of study. Maternal weight, height and body mass Index (BMI) was calculated. Their blood glucose and HbA1c levels were measured.

APGAR scores at 1st minute and 5th minutes, birth weight & length was recorded and Ponderal index (PI) was calculated. It is a weight-height related parameter used to predict fetal growth pattern in small-for-gestational age infants and for large-for-gestational age (LGA) infants. It is calculated using formula: $PI = \text{weight (g)} \times 100 / (\text{height, in cm})^3$.²¹ After resection of the umbilical cord, the cord stump remaining on the placenta was

cleaned and 2ml of blood was collected and analyzed for Platelet profile (Platelet count, Mean platelet volume (MPV) Platelet distribution width (PDW) using automated hematological analyzer.

Statistical Analysis

Data were recorded using the SPSS 15.0 statistical software package (SPSS Inc.,

Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive data was expressed as Mean±S.D and student's t-test was used for comparison between the groups. p-value <0.05 was considered to be significant.

Results

Table 1: Maternal characteristics of case and control groups

Characteristics	Diabetic pregnant women (n=50) Mean±SD	Normal pregnant women (n=50) Mean±SD	p-value
Age of mother (yrs)	32.8 ±4.2	30.2±2.6	>0.05
Gestation at delivery (wks)	38.4±1.1	38.8±1.2	>0.05
Body mass Index (kg/ m2)	25.5±2.7	22.4±1.5	<0.05
HbA1c	5.5± 1.1	4.6±0.5	<0.05

The result showed that there was significant difference in maternal BMI and HbA1c between the study groups.

Table 2: Apgar score assessment at birth

Apgar score		Newborn of Diabetic mother (n=50)	Newborn of healthy mother (n=50)
Apgar 1 min	8-10	28	32
	5-7	15	16
	<5	7	2
Apgar 5min	8-10	35	40
	5-7	13	10
	<5	2	-

Apgar score assessment at birth did not show any significant difference between two groups.

Table 3: Anthropometric parameters of newborn at birth

Characteristics	Newborn of Diabetic mother (n=50) Mean±SD	Newborn of healthy mother(n=50) Mean±SD	p-value
Neonate Birth weight (gms)	3050.2±535.5	2952.8±560.8	>0.05
Ponderal Index (g/cm ³)	2.6±0.2	2.8±0.2	>0.05

Demographic characteristics of the newborn between two groups were not significant.

Table 4: Cord blood Platelet profile in neonate of diabetic and non- diabetic mothers

Parameters	Newborn of Diabetic mother (n=50) Mean±SD	Newborn of healthy mother (n=50) Mean±SD	p-value
Platelet count Lakh/ mm ³	1.99±8.82	2.40±6.34	<0.05
MPV fL	8.42±1.52	7.33±0.57	<0.05
PDW%	13.37±4.57	13.30±0.70	>0.05

Platelet count was significantly higher in control group than in diabetic group. MPV was significantly higher in IDM group. There was no significant difference in Platelet distribution width (PDW) between two groups.

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is the commonest endocrinal disorder, causing considerable morbidity and mortality to both mother and fetus. [22] Its incidence is increasing among urban population at an alarming rate, due to stress inducing life style. It involves derangement of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism characterized by hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia and negative nitrogen balance. [23] The term "Infant from diabetic mother" (IDM) refers to those from pregnancies complicated by diabetes mellitus (DM type 1, type 2) or gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). [24] GDM-complicated pregnancies are considered high-risk, as they have been linked to adverse outcomes, both maternal and fetal. Maternal complications during pregnancy include spontaneous miscarriage, and pre-eclampsia/pregnancy-induced hypertension; with long-term recurrent GDM in subsequent pregnancies, type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome may occur. The offspring of a mother with GDM has immediate and long-term complications, such as macrosomia due to hyperinsulinism, increased risk for trauma at birth, hypoglycemia, hypocalcemia, jaundice, cardiomyopathy, respiratory distress and an increased risk of congenital malformations and type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome in the long term. All

of these are responsible for the higher mortality and morbidity rates observed in these neonates, which are directly proportional to the maternal glycemic control. [25]

The result showed that there was significant difference in maternal BMI and HbA1c between the two groups. Apgar score assessment at birth did not show any significant difference between two groups. Demographic characteristics of the newborns between two groups were not significant. Platelet count was significantly higher in control group than in diabetic group. MPV was significantly higher in IDM group. There was no significant difference in Platelet distribution width (PDW) between two groups. MPV is a marker of platelet function and activation. [22,23] Patients with high MPV had low platelet counts. It has been reported that platelet survival is shorter in diabetic patients. [26] This may be explained by variables such as platelet production and mean platelet survival. The platelet distribution width displays a good correlation with the MPV. [22,23] The platelet count is slightly lower in pregnant than in non-pregnant women. [27] It also decrease with increase in duration of pregnancy. [28] Normally interleukins, specially IL-6 is required to convert uncommitted stem cell to committed stem cells of megakaryocytic series. The IL-6 in neonate of diabetic mother loses its hemopoietic potency due to immunomodulatory effect of diabetic maternal IL-6 resulting in decreased platelet count. It is also attributed to fetal hypoxia due to placental abnormality in diabetic group. Kinalski et al study in diabetic mothers

suggested that their fetuses experience increased oxidative stress. [29] The results show that acetoacetate, but not β -hydroxybutyrate, increased MCP-1 secretion in U937 monocytes exposed to high glucose.

Patients with diabetes have increased platelet activation compared to non-diabetic. [23,30] Their hyperactivity may potentially have a role in the development of vasculopathies. [19,20] It is accompanied by increased thromboxane synthesis and/or decreased prostacycline production. Larger platelets are both more reactive and aggregable. [31] They contain denser granules, secrete more serotonin and b-thromboglobulin, and produce more thromboxane A₂ than smaller platelets. This relates to a relationship between platelet function and micro and macrovascular complications of diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion

Mean Platelet volume and other platelet-related parameters is a simple procedure, available in most hospital laboratories. It is useful for representing the potential oxidative stress of IDM. Hence, there is need to create more awareness by pre-pregnancy counselling of know diabetics as well as screening for potential gestational diabetics. MPV may be used as a marker for follow-up of diabetic patients.

References

1. Yogev Y, Visser GH. Obesity, gestational diabetes and pregnancy outcome. In Seminars in Fetal and Neonatal Medicine 2009 Apr 1 (Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 77-84). WB Saunders.
2. Agoudeiros M, Reinking BE, Koppenhafer SL, Segar JL, Scholz TD. Programming of adult cardiovascular disease following exposure to late-gestation hyperglycemia. Neonatology. 2011;100(2):198-205.
3. Koskinen A, Laiho A, Lukkarinen H, Käpä P, Soukka H. Maternal hyperglycemia modifies extracellular matrix signaling pathways in neonatal rat lung. Neonatology. 2010;98(4):387-96.
4. Newton CA, Raskin P. Diabetic ketoacidosis in type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus: clinical and biochemical differences. Archives of internal medicine. 2004 Sep 27;164 (17):1925-31.
5. Jain SK, Kannan K, Lim G, Matthews-Greer J, McVie R, Bocchini Jr JA. Elevated blood interleukin-6 levels in hyperketonemic type 1 diabetic patients and secretion by acetoacetate-treated cultured U937 monocytes. Diabetes Care. 2003 Jul 1;26(7):2139-43.
6. Jain SK, Kannan K, Lim G, McVie R, Bocchini Jr JA. Hyperketonemia increases tumor necrosis factor- α secretion in cultured U937 monocytes and type 1 diabetic patients and is apparently mediated by oxidative stress and cAMP deficiency. Diabetes. 2002 Jul 1;51(7):2287-93.
7. Rains JL, Jain SK. Hyperketonemia increases monocyte adhesion to endothelial cells and is mediated by LFA-1 expression in monocytes and ICAM-1 expression in endothelial cells. American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism. 2011 Aug;301(2):E298-306.
8. Plows JF, Stanley JL, Baker PN, Reynolds CM, Vickers MH. The pathophysiology of gestational diabetes mellitus. International journal of molecular sciences. 2018 Oct 26;19 (11):3342.
9. Westermeier F, Sáez T, Arroyo P, Toledo F, Gutiérrez J, Sanhueza C, Pardo F, Leiva A, Sobrevia L. Insulin receptor isoforms: an integrated view focused on gestational diabetes mellitus. Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews. 2016 May;32(4):350-65.
10. Santilli F, Liani R, Di Fulvio P, Formoso G, Simeone P, Tripaldi R, Ueland T, Aukrust P, Davi G. Increased circulating resistin is

- associated with insulin resistance, oxidative stress and platelet activation in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Thrombosis and haemostasis*. 2016;116(12):1089-99.
11. Xu J, Zhao YH, Chen YP, Yuan XL, Wang J, Zhu H, Lu CM. Maternal circulating concentrations of tumor necrosis factor-alpha, leptin, and adiponectin in gestational diabetes mellitus: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Scientific World Journal*. 2014 Jan 1;2014.
 12. Gerrits AJ, Gitz E, Koekman CA, Visseren FL, van Haeften TW, Akkerman JW. Induction of insulin resistance by the adipokines resistin, leptin, plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 and retinol binding protein 4 in human megakaryocytes. *Haematologica*. 2012 Aug;97(8):1149.
 13. Pantham P, Aye IL, Powell TL. Inflammation in maternal obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus. *Placenta*. 2015 Jul 1;36(7):709-15.
 14. Gussi IL. OP16. 03: Fetal cerebral perfusion in the third trimester of pregnancies with controlled maternal insulin-dependent-diabetes (IDD). *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2011 Oct;38(S1):101-.
 15. Platt MW, Deshpande S. Metabolic adaptation at birth. In *Seminars in Fetal and Neonatal Medicine* 2005 Aug 1 (Vol. 10, No. 4, pp. 341-350). WB Saunders.
 16. Ogata ES. Perinatal morbidity in offspring of diabetic mothers. *Diabetes Reviews*. 1995;3(4):652.
 17. Pöyhönen-Alho M, Joutsu-Korhonen L, Lassila R, Kaaja R. Alterations of sympathetic nervous system, coagulation and platelet function in gestational diabetes. *Blood coagulation & fibrinolysis*. 2012 Sep 1;23(6):508-13.
 18. Stein PD, Goldman J, Matta F and Yaekoub AY. Diabetes mellitus and risk of venous thromboembolism. *Am J Med Sci* 2009; 337: 259-64.
 19. Farhan S, Winzer C, Tura A, Quehenberger P, Bieglmaier C, Wagner OF, Huber K, Waldhäusl W, Pacini G, Kautzky-Willer A. Fibrinolytic dysfunction in insulin-resistant women with previous gestational diabetes. *European journal of clinical investigation*. 2006 May; 36(5):345-52.
 20. Strauss T, Maayan-Metzger A, Simchen MJ, Morag I, Shenkmean B, Kuint J, Kenet G. Impaired platelet function in neonates born to mothers with diabetes or hypertension during pregnancy. *Klinische Pädiatrie*. 2010 May;222(03):154-7.
 21. Armangil D, Yurdakok M, Korkmaz A, Yigit S and Tekinalp G. Ponderal index of large-for-gestational age infants: comparison between infants of diabetic and non-diabetic mothers. *Turk J Pediatr*. 2011 ;53(2):169-72.
 22. Bozkurt N, Yılmaz E, Biri A, Taner Z, Himmetoğlu Ö. The mean platelet volume in gestational diabetes. *Journal of thrombosis and thrombolysis*. 2006 Aug;22:51-4.
 23. Hekimsoy Z, Payzin B, Örnek T, Kandoğan G. Mean platelet volume in Type 2 diabetic patients. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications*. 2004 May 1;18(3):173-6.
 24. HAPO Study Cooperative Research Group, Matzger BE, Lowe LP, Dyer AR, Trimble ER, Chaovariner U, Coustan DR. Hyperglycemia and adverse pregnancy outcome. *N Engl J Med*. 2008;358:1991-2002.
 25. Cowett, R.M. The Infant of the Diabetic Mother. *Neo Rev*. 2002, 3, e173–e189.
 26. Coban E, Bostan F, Ozdogan M. The mean platelet volume in subjects with impaired fasting glucose. *Platelets*. 2006 Feb 1;17(1):67-9.
 27. Abbassi-Ghanavati M, Greer LG, Cunningham FG. Pregnancy and laboratory studies: a reference table for clinicians. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2009 Dec 1;114(6):1326-31.

28. Akingbola TS, Adewole IF, Adesina OA, Afolabi KA, Fehintola FA, Bamgboye EA, Aken'ova YA, Shokunbi WA, Anwo JA, Nwegbu MM. Haematological profile of healthy pregnant women in Ibadan, south-western Nigeria. *Journal of obstetrics and gynaecology*. 2006 Jan 1;26(8): 763-9.
29. Kinalski M, Śledziewski A, Telejko B, Kowalska I, Krętownski A, Zarzycki W, Kinalska I. Lipid peroxidation, antioxidant defence and acid-base status in cord blood at birth: the influence of diabetes. *Hormone and Metabolic Research*. 2001 Apr;33(04): 227-31.
30. Erikçi AA, Muşcu M, Dündar Ö, Öztürk A. Could mean platelet volume be a predictive marker for gestational diabetes mellitus?. *Hematology*. 2008 Feb 1;13(1):46-8.
31. Bath PM, Butterworth RJ. Platelet size: measurement, physiology and vascular disease. *Blood coagulation & fibrinolysis*. 1996 Mar 1;7(2):157-61.